

Introduction to the Fish Nutrition, Feed Formulation, and Feeding Conversion

Joshi P. S.*

Post Doctoral Fellow, Srinivas University, Mangalore, Karnataka, India

P. S. Aithal

Vice-Chancellor, Srinivas University, Mangalore, Karnataka, India

* Email: psjoshi009@gmail.com

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Abstract

A variety of fish feed are readily available in market. They come in many different shapes and sizes. However, not all fish feed may be suitable for every fish species. It is important to recognize the right type of food for farmed fish. Feeding fish a balanced diet is essential for their proper growth and well-being. The diet that they eat will have a direct impact on their health. Unlike fish in their natural environment, fish in captivity rely on their feed for their nutrients. In all these concern, present paper aims to explore the details about fish feed formulation, feed types, feeding pattern, feed conversion and overall quality maintenance.

INTRODUCTION

Good nutrition in fish culture is essential to the economic production of a healthy, high-quality product with rich survival, growth, reproductive performance, spawning success, and body composition (Kaushik *et al.*, 2011). In aquaculture, nutrition is critical because feed typically represents approximately 50 percent of the variable production cost. Fish nutrition has advanced dramatically in recent years with the development of new, balanced commercial diets that promote optimal fish growth and health (Makode, 2017). The development of new species-specific feed formulations supports the aquaculture industry as it expands to satisfy an increasing demand for affordable, safe, high-quality fish and seafood products. Jhingran (1991) noted that formulated feed plays a vital role in semi-intensive fish culture, where it is required to maintain a high density of fish than the natural fertility of water. Thus supplementary feed can be considered as a most desirable measure for increasing fish yield.

Nowadays, feed costs make up a significant fraction of total fish production costs. Optimizing growth rates and feed efficiency in fish depends on the way in which feed is made, availability of feed, the amount of food delivered, feeding frequency, timing of each feeding periods and the characteristics of the diets (Ali, and Hoq, 2010). In most traditional aquaculture practices, herbivorous or omnivorous species have been preferred as they feed on natural food in water. Thus growth can be easily enhanced through cheap supplementary feeding and fertilization (Pillay, 2001). But carnivorous species such as catfishes, murrels, etc. need a high protein diet. New and Wijkstrom (2002) mentioned that on the basis of growth rate, feed conversion, and nutrient retention is protein, lipid, carbohydrate and gross energy.

Among all the nutrients, Protein is by far the essential nutrient needed for growth being efficiently utilized by catfish and is very expensive. An inclusion levels, quality of protein and the ratio of protein to another dietary nutrient significantly

alter the growth pattern of fish (Butle *et al.*, 2018; Rodge *et al.*, 2020). Traditionally, fish meal is the preferred dietary protein source for many farmed fish species due to its amino acid profile, vitamin mineral content, high digestibility, palatability and unidentified growth factors (Miles and Chapman, 2006) and is currently the primary source of protein fed to farm fish, especially carnivorous fishes (Zhou *et al.*, 2004).

In this concern, a present study aim to describe the role of fish nutrition, feed formulation and feeding conversion in aquaculture.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The present study is a review on the progress in the role of herbal feeds in freshwater aquaculture. It has been compiled primarily from articles and technical reports published in scientific journals. The related information has been compiled from important literature published until 2021.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Good nutrition in animal production systems is essential to economical production of a healthy, high-quality product. In aquaculture, nutrition is critical because feed typically represents approximately 50 percent of the variable production cost. Fish nutrition has advanced dramatically in recent years with the development of new, balanced commercial diets that promote optimal fish growth and health. According to Craig and Kuhn (2017), the development of new species-specific diet formulations supports the aquaculture industry as it expands to satisfy increasing demand for affordable, safe, high-quality fish and seafood products.

Fish feed formulation

Manufactured feeds are an important part of modern commercial aquaculture, providing the balanced nutrition needed by farmed fish. The feeds, in the form of granules or pellets, provide the nutrition in a stable and concentrated form, enabling the fish to feed efficiently and grow to their full potential. The fishmeal and fish oil were key components of the feeds for these species. They are combined with other ingredients such as vegetable proteins, cereal grains, vitamins and minerals and formed into feed pellets. Wheat, for example, is widely used as it helps to bind the ingredients in the pellets. Other forms of fish feed being used include feeds made entirely with vegetable materials for species such as carp, moist feeds preferred by some species which easier to make but more difficult to store and trash fish that is fish caught and fed

directly to larger species being raised in aquaculture pens. Modern fish feeds are made by grinding and mixing together ingredients such as fishmeal, vegetable proteins and binding agents such as wheat (Craig and Kunh (2017),

In the current technology, fish feed extruders play a key role in production lines. Although the majority of the process of the fish feed production occurs in the extruder, grinding and mixing can highly affect the quality of the final product. Water is added and the resulting paste is extruded through holes in a metal plate. The diameter of the holes is usually the most important parameter that sets the diameter of the pellets, which can range from less than a millimetre to over a centimetre. As the feed is extruded it is cut to form pellets of the required length. The pellets are dried and oils are added. Adjusting parameters such as temperature and pressure enables the manufacturers to make pellets that suit different fish farming methods, for example feeds that float or sink slowly and feeds suited to recirculation systems. The dry feed pellets are stable for relatively long periods, for convenient storage and distribution. Feeds are delivered in bulk, in large bags for use in fish hatcheries (Sarker *et al.*, 2020).

Fish feed ingredients

According to Craig and Kuhn (2017) and Shukla *et al.*, (2019) following components can be added in various ratios to meet the requirements of different fish species. Fish in various stages of their growth will also require different ingredients in different ratios as well. In general, carnivorous fish, juvenile fish, and fry will require higher protein content.

Proteins: Because protein is the most expensive component of fish feed, it is important to accurately determine the protein requirements for each species and life stage cultured. Proteins are formed by linkages of individual amino acids. Although more than 200 amino acids occur in nature, only about 20 amino acids are common. Of these, 10 are essential (indispensable) amino acids that cannot be synthesized by fish. The 10 essential amino acids that must be supplied by the diet are methionine, arginine, threonine, tryptophan, histidine, isoleucine, lysine, leucine, valine, and phenylalanine. Of these, lysine and methionine are often the first limiting amino acids. Protein requirements can be varied for different fish species. Protein requirements are generally higher for smaller as well as early life stage fish.

As fish grow larger, their protein requirements usually decrease. Protein requirements also vary with the rearing environment, water temperature, and water quality, as well as the genetic composition and feeding rates of the fish. Protein is used for fish growth if adequate levels of fats and carbohydrates (energy) are present in the diet. If not, the more expensive protein can be used for energy and life support rather than growth.

Lipids: These are high-energy nutrients that can be utilized to partially spare (substitute for) protein in aquaculture feeds. Lipids have about twice the energy density of proteins and carbohydrates. Lipids typically make up about 7-15 percent of fish diets, supply essential fatty acids, and serve as transporters for fat-soluble vitamins. A recent trend in fish feeds is to use higher levels of lipids in the diet. Increasing dietary lipids can help reduce the high costs of feed by partially sparing protein in the feed, problems such as excessive fat deposition in the liver can decrease fish health, quality, and shelf life of the final product. Lipids, or fats, will typically comprise about 10-15% of the feed. For herbivorous fish, the typical range is 3-5%. This is a high-energy ingredient. It provides approximately twice the energy of proteins and carbohydrates. The source of lipid is typically fish oil. The oil is extracted from other fish such as sardines. Alternative to fish oil includes vegetable oils.

Carbohydrates: Carbohydrate is an economical source of energy for fish. It helps to reduce the feed cost. It can be useful as a binding agent when manufacturing the feed, especially for feed that are designed to float. Carbohydrates make up 20-30% of much commercial feed. While carbohydrate in fish feed is economical, some fish do not tolerate it in high amounts. Enzymes for carbohydrate digestion are not present in the same amount for all fish. If the concentration of carbohydrates is too high, fish can develop signs of ill health. For example, excessive fat in liver are known to develop in some fish. In general, mono or d-saccharide is utilized better than polysaccharide. During the manufacturing process, if the starch is cooked, it can make it more biologically available to fish. In general, carnivorous fish and fry digest carbohydrates less efficiently than omnivorous and herbivorous fish.

Vitamins: Vitamins are organic compounds that are necessary for the growth and health of the fish. Key vitamins for fish include A, B1, B2, B3, B5, B6, B12, Biotin, C, Choline, D3, E, Folic acid, Inositol, and K. Unfortunately, many vitamins do not remain

stable for very long in processed feed. Oxidation can degrade vitamins very quickly. For example, the vitamin C content in a open container of flake food can start degrading within a month. The deficiency of each vitamin has specific symptoms, but reduced growth is the most common symptom of any vitamin deficiency. Scoliosis and dark coloration may result from deficiencies of ascorbic acid and folic acid, respectively.

Minerals: Minerals are inorganic elements that are necessary for the fish to function. Maintenance of cells, immune system, and bones, all require minerals. Key minerals needed by fish are calcium and phosphorus. Small traces of sodium, magnesium, iron, iodine, chloride, copper, potassium, sulfur, and zinc are also needed. Fortunately, minerals have a longer shelf life compared to vitamins.

Binding Agent: The binding agent provides water stability to the feed. Typically, only a small amount is required, less than 1%. Guar gum and Carboxy Methyl cellulose are binding agents commonly used.

Preservatives: Preservatives help extend the shelf life of processed fish feed. Preservatives can consist of anti-microbials and antioxidants. Common sources of anti-microbial are sodium benzoate, sorbic acid. They are typically added in very small amounts, less than 0.1%. Common sources of antioxidants are Vitamin E, butylated hydroxyanisole (BHA), butylated hydroxytoluene (BHT), and ethoxyquin.

Attractants: Attractants are commonly added to fish feed to make it more palatable. This can consist of approximately 5% of the feed. Common sources of attractants are hydrolysates and condensed fish solubles.

Energy: Dietary nutrients are essential for the construction of living tissues. They also are a source of stored energy for fish digestion, absorption, growth, reproduction, and other life processes. The nutritional value of a dietary ingredient is in part dependent on its ability to supply energy. Physiological fuel values are used to calculate and balance available energy values in prepared diets. To create an optimum diet, the ratio of protein to energy must be determined independently for each fish species. Excess energy relative to protein content in the diet can result in high lipid deposition. Because fish feed in order to meet their energy requirements, diets with excessive energy levels may result in decreased feed intake and reduced weight gain. Similarly, a diet with

inadequate energy content can result in reduced weight gain because the fish cannot eat enough feed to satisfy their energy requirements for growth. Properly formulated prepared feeds have a well-balanced energy-to-protein ratio.

Growth promoters

Growth promoters are feed additives for fish. Different categories of feed additives for fishes are referred to as growth promoters. Broadly they are of two types- Antibiotics and non-antibiotic (natural) growth promoters. The natural growth promoters are commonly regarded as favorable alternatives to antibiotic growth promoters in livestock production. The natural growth promoters include predominantly organic acids, probiotics, prebiotics, synbiotics, phytochemicals, tannins, feed enzymes and immune stimulants. The mode of action of the growth promoters are mentioned below (Steiner, 2006; Thorarinsdottir, *et al.*, 2011).

Acidifiers: Acidifiers, such as organic acids or their salts, are used to prevent microbial degradation of raw materials or finished feeds, especially under poor storage conditions like high moisture content, high levels of contamination with molds. Moreover, acidifiers may improve growth performance through establishment of low gastrointestinal pH conditions which support endogenous digestive enzymes and reduce undesired gut microorganisms. Many dietary acidifiers are based on propionic acid, formic acid, lactic acid and others, either as single components or in combination. Some acidifiers also contain inorganic acids like phosphoric acid.

Probiotics: These are live microorganisms or viable spores which support the development of a beneficial gut microflora. Probiotic bacteria from the genera *Lactobacillus*, *Bifidobacterium*, *Enterococcus* which counteract undesired microorganisms such as *Salmonella* or *E. coli* by blocking receptors on the gut wall, production of antimicrobial substances or activation of the immune system.

Prebiotics: These are carbohydrates which are indigestible for the host animal. On the other hand, they are selectively fermented by beneficial gut bacteria and, therefore, support a healthy gut microflora. These include fructose oligosaccharides including inulin, transgalactose oligosaccharides, xylooligosaccharides and soy oligosaccharides such as stachyose, verbascose and raffinose. Mannan oligosaccharides are sometimes included as prebiotics but are not fermentable.

Synbiotics: Combined administration of probiotics and prebiotics, referred to as synbiotics, is supposed

to cause synergistic effects in terms of gut health and performance.

Phytochemicals: These are derived from herbs, spices or aromatic plants and have shown antimicrobial, antifungal, antiviral, antioxidant or sedative properties. They are known for their appetizing effects, since they increase the palatability of the feed and stimulate endogenous digestive enzymes. Moreover, phytochemicals have a pronounced impact on the gut microflora.

Tannins: Tannins are polyphenolic compounds produced by plants, ranging in concentrations from <2% to more than 20% of dry weight and may protect plants from herbivore, increase resistance against pathogens, or protect tissues such as wood against decay. These are effective to reduce and control infection. Moreover are considered a natural alternative to antibiotic growth promoters due to the difficulty of bacteria to develop resistance against the diverse range of molecules that contain these plant compounds.

Feed enzymes: Animal feeds contain varying levels of indigestible nutrients and undesired components such as fiber, phytate or proteins with antigenic effects. Different feed enzymes such as, carbohydrases, phytases or proteases, can be included in feeds to improve the utilization of energy and nutrients or to degrade several undesired components. Moreover, enzymes like amylases and lipases can be added to the feed of young animals in order to support the endogenous enzyme secretions.

Immune stimulants: Different feed additives may function as stimulator or modulator of immunity processes. Specific cell wall fragments from bacteria or yeasts or sea algae may induce activation of immune cells like macrophages, lymphocytes.

Sources of nutrients

Bhosale *et al.*, (2010), Shukla *et al.*, (2019) and Gündoğdu *et al.*, (2021) mentioned the following common sources of nutrients

Fish meal: It has two basic types: (a) those produced from fishery wastes associated with the processing of fish for human consumption (such as salmon and tuna) and (b) those from specific fish (herring, menhaden and pollack) which are harvested solely for the purpose of producing fish meal.

Shrimp meal: It is made from cull shrimp that are being processed before freezing or from whole shrimp that is not of suitable quality for human consumption. The material to be made into shrimp meal is dried (sun-dried or by using a dryer) and then ground.

Shrimp meal is a source of pigments that enhances the desirable color in the tissues of fish. It is also a secondary supplemental protein source for fish.

Squid meal: It is made from squid viscera portions from cannery plants including the eggs and testis. Squid Meal is a highly digestible protein source for fish which provides a full range of amino acids, vitamins, minerals and cholesterol (1.0–1.5%) of cholesterol suitable for fish fry and young fish.

Brine shrimp: It is a common food source for fish that are available in adult-form, as eggs or freeze-dried. Brine shrimp is a source of protein, carotene (a color enhancer) and acts as a natural laxative in fish digestive systems. Brine shrimps can also supply the fish with vegetable matter due to their consumption of algae.

Soybean meal: It is a high protein source for fish and has become a substitute for traditionally-used marine animal meals.

Spirulina: It is blue-green plant plankton rich in raw protein, vitamins A, B1, B2, B6, B12, C and E, beta-carotene, color enhancing pigments, a whole range of minerals, essential fatty acids and eight amino acids required for complete nutrition.

Whole wheat: It is not the best source of energy in fish but is an excellent source of roughage for fish. It is a natural source of carbohydrates and vitamin E which promotes growth and enhances coloration.

Some alternate sources: The gluten meal, groundnut cake meal, blood meal, feather meal, meat and bone meal, leguminous seed meal, poultry by-product, brewer's grains, bagasse, Molasses, vegetable waste, medicinal herbs etc. can also be the best easily available sources.

Types of fish feed

Prepared foods are those foods that are non-living and are made by the aquarist or bought already prepared for consumption for fish (Axelrod, 1996).

On the basis of preparation

Dry feed: It is a type of proprietary or artificially manufactured fish food consumed by a wide variety of tropical and saltwater fish and invertebrates. It is ideally suited to top dwellers and mid-water fish though numerous bottom dwelling species consume flake food once it has settled on the bottom. Flake food is baked to remove moisture, ensuring a longer shelf life. Generally the more moisture a particular example of fish food contains, the more readily it will deteriorate in quality. Dry foods are also available as pellets, sticks, tablets, granules, and

wafers, manufactured to float or sink, depending on the species they are designed to feed.

Vacation feed: It is also known as food blocks or weekend blocks for smaller versions), are designed to be placed inside the aquarium to forgo feeding while the owner is absent. These blocks release small amounts of food as they dissolve. Food blocks can be a good choice for smaller tropical fish, but can pollute the water if the tank is neglected for too long.

Medicated feed: It is a safe and effective method to deliver medication to fish. One advantage is that medicated food does not contaminate the aquatic environment and also, unlike bath treatments, does not negatively affect fish, filtration and algae growth in the aquarium. The parasites will get treated spot on by medicated food, because the fish is ingesting it.

Freeze-dried feed: It is primarily developed for tropical and marine fish and are useful in providing variety to the diet or specialist feeding needs of some species. These include tubifex worms, mosquito larvae, bloodworms, water fleas along with brine shrimp.

Frozen feed: Perishable food can be preserved by frozen storage, and is often sold in blister packs. These can contain a variety of ingredients such as bloodworms, Daphnia, or brine shrimp, and are commonly used to feed such fish as Discus which require a high protein diet. Often fed on beef heart fish food within the aquaculture industry, the discus fish are not the only fish which can benefit from a high quality prepared frozen mixture such as beef heart, although by far these are the fish most associated with this particular frozen food.

Colour enhancing feed: Color is very important to ornamental fish. Color enhancers are popular for tropical fish and koi fish food. In order to allow the fish to exhibit the most vibrant color, carotenoids are added as an enhancer. In nature, fish would be able to eat plants and invertebrates that are high in carotenoids such as astaxanthin and canthaxanthin.

On the basis of structure

Pellet Food: Pellet food is a popular type of fish food, especially for feeding larger aquarium fish and farmed fish. The manufacturer will grind up the feed components, extrude it with heat and pressure, then produce pellets in various sizes. Some are designed to float on water, while others are designed to sink.

Pellet food decomposes slower in water compared to other fish food. Therefore, the fish has a better chance of eating the pellet before it decomposes and pollutes the water. In general, pellet food has a longer shelf life than other types of feed. The smaller surface area reduces the oxidation rate.

Flake Food: Flake food is another popular type of fish food, especially for aquarium fish. Flake food will float for a certain amount of time, then slowly sink to the bottom. This gives a chance for all types of fish at all levels of the aquarium to feed. Flake food is great for community fish tanks where different species of fish are co-existing.

Powdered Food: Powdered food, or fry food, is often used in fish hatcheries to feed juvenile fish. The dry powder can be directly fed to the fish, or mixed in water before feeding it to the fish. Powdered food can pollute the tank water very quickly. Overfeeding should be avoided, and any excess should be removed immediately.

On the basis of nature

Floating feed: In general floating feeds offer numerous advantages over their sinking counterparts. Raw materials are propelled by screws along the barrel of the extruder machine to cook the materials at 120-175°C for about 30 seconds. The homogenous cooked mixture is forced through a die at high pressure. The material expands because of the pressure difference. Floating feeds are more digestible as a result of cooking process and the heat and pressure deactivate destructive enzymes as well. Increased starch gelatinization helps the feed to be more stable in water by disintegrating less quickly that gives enough time to the fish to take the meal completely. Moreover, the farmer can directly observe the feeding intensity of his fish and adjust feeding rates accordingly determining whether feeding rates are too low or too high is important in maximizing fish growth and feed use efficiency. Another side effect is that farmers can visually monitor the health condition of the reared fish as they come to the surface to take feed. In contrast, floating feed can be detrimental with respect to consumption by competitors and some fish species.

Sinking feeds: Sinking feeds are solid feed pellets that submerged during application. Bottom feeder shrimp, for example, prefer sinking pellets (density greater than that of water, 1 g/cm³) and will not accept a floating feed. The farmer cannot always estimate feeding rates properly in relation to the biomass present in his pond and feeding whether too low or too high than the actual requirement. It

cause lower weight gain in a particular age and enlarge the culture period when feeding rate is low. In the other hand, overfeeding cause a subsequent loss of feed supplied as well as deteriorating water quality that may results in several problems.

Live fish feed

According to Craig and Kunh (2017), living feed is one of the best sources of fish food. Fish are opportunistic feeders. In nature, many fish will eat insects and worms regularly. Since live food is not readily available in an enclosed environment, it can be beneficial to add it as a part of their diet. Feeding live food may be necessary for fish with specialized needs such as some carnivorous fish, picky eaters, and fry. Many wild caught specimen that have not been able to adjust to processed dry feed will most likely require live food.

Not only does live food mimic the feeding habit of fish in their natural environment, but live food can provide many benefits that commercial feeds have not been able to replicate. Many fry that have been grown with a supplement of live food have proved to have exceptionally better survival rates and grow to become one of the most robust specimen. Live organisms that are suitable for as feed include bloodworms, mealworms, blackworms, tubifex, glassworm, grindal worms, white worms, redworms, daphnia, gammarus, among many others. Feeding live food at least twice a week is recommended for most fish. If these invertebrates are collected from a garden or outdoor pond, be mindful of potential risks such as parasites and harmful chemicals. It is possible to grow your own live fish food such as white worms. Live food is a great way to supplement a varied diet.

Maintaining feed quality

A variety of factors govern the quality and wholesomeness of aquafeeds. Feeding stuffs origin, processing, handling and storage, as well as many other factors related to the market, can affect at different levels both quality and safety of feed (Pinotti and Dell'Orto, 2011). Feed quality can be ensured initially by using good quality ingredients. Purchase of raw materials must conformed adequate quality, traceability, environmental sustainability and safety standards. Commercial fish feed is usually purchased by large farms as bulk feed in truckloads and stored in outside bins. Smaller farms often buy prepared feed in 50-pound bags. Bagged feed should be kept out of direct sunlight and as cool as possible. Vitamins, proteins, and lipids are

especially heat-sensitive and can be readily denatured by high storage temperatures. High moisture stimulates mold growth and feed decomposition. Avoid unnecessary handling and damage to the feed bags that could break the pellets and create fines (powder) that will not be consumed by fish (Luciano and Vittorio, 2011).

According to Pinotti and Dell'Orto (2011), feed should not be stored longer than 90 to 100 days and should be inventoried regularly. Bags should not be stacked more than 10 high because the excessive weight from the upper bags will crush pellets in lower bags, creating excess fines (dust). Older feed should be used first, and all feed should be regularly inspected for mold prior to feeding. All moldy feed should be discarded immediately. Mice, rats, roaches, and other pests should be strictly controlled in the feed storage area because they consume and contaminate feed and transmit diseases.

Feeding rate, frequency and timing

According to Craig and Kunh (2017), feeding rates and frequencies are in part a function of fish size. Small larval fish and fry need to be fed a high-protein diet frequently and usually in excess. Small fish have a high energy demand and must eat nearly continuously and be fed almost hourly. Feeding small fish in excess is not as much of a problem as overfeeding larger fish because small fish require only a small amount of feed relative to the volume of water in the culture system. As fish grow, feeding rates, frequencies, and feed protein content should be reduced. However, rather than switching to a lower protein diet, feeding less may allow the grower to use the same feed (protein level) throughout the grow-out period, thereby simplifying feed inventory and storage.

Feeding fish is labor-intensive and expensive. Feeding frequency is dependent on labor availability, farm size, production system, and the fish species and sizes grown. Large catfish farms with many ponds usually feed only once per day because of time and labor limitations, while smaller farms may feed twice per day. Generally, growth and feed conversion increase with feeding frequency. In indoor, intensive fish culture systems, fish might be fed as many as five times per day in order to maximize growth at optimum temperatures. Many factors affect the feeding rates of fish. These include life stage, time of day, season, water temperature, dissolved oxygen levels, and other water quality variables. For example, feeding fish

grown in ponds early in the morning when the lowest dissolved oxygen levels occur is not advisable. In contrast, in recirculating aquaculture systems where oxygen is continuously supplied, fish can be fed at nearly any time. During the winter and at low water temperatures, feeding rates of warm-water fish in ponds decline and should decrease proportionally.

Feed acceptability, palatability, and digestibility vary with the ingredients and feed quality. Fish farmers pay careful attention to feeding activity in order to help determine feed acceptance, calculate feed conversion ratios and feed efficiencies, monitor feed costs, and track feed demand throughout the year. Published feeding rate tables are available for most commonly cultured fish species. Farmers can calculate optimum feeding rates based on the average size in length or weight and the number of fish in the tank, raceway, or pond (New, 1987). Farmed fish typically are fed 1-5 percent of their body weight per day.

Feed conversion and efficiency assessment

According to Craig and Kunh (2017), Butle *et al.* (2018) and Rodge *et al.* (2020), feed is expensive, feed conversion ratio or feed efficiency are important calculations for the used as efficiently as possible. Feed conversion ratio is calculated as the weight of the feed fed to the fish divided by the weight of fish growth. For example, if fish are fed 10 pounds of feed and then exhibit a 5-pound weight gain, the FCR is $10/5 = 2$. An FCR of 1.5-2.0 is considered good growth for most species. Trout, salmon, and tilapia tend to have lower FCR values ranging from 0.9 to 1.3. Feed efficiency is simply the reciprocal of the feed conversion ratio ($1/FCR$). In the example above, the FE is $5/10 = 50$ percent. Therefore, if fish are fed 12 pounds of feed and exhibit a 4-pound weight gain, the FE = $4/12 = 33$ percent. An FE greater than 50 percent is generally considered acceptable. In addition to growth, some of the energy in feed is used by the fish for metabolic and digestive processing, respiration, nerve impulses, salt balance, swimming, and other living activities. Feed conversion ratios will vary among species, sizes, and activity levels of fish, environmental parameters, and the culture system used.

Water quality and waste management

Claude and Lichtkoppler (1979) mentioned that the water quality includes all physical, chemical, and biological factors that influence the

beneficial use of water. Where fish culture is concerned, any characteristic of water that affects the survival, reproduction, growth, production, or management of fish in any way is a water quality variable. Obviously, there are many water quality variables in pond fish culture. Fortunately, only a few of these normally play an important role. These are the variables that fish culturists should concentrate on, and attempt to control to some extent by management techniques. All other things being equal, a pond with good water quality will produce more and healthier fish than a pond with poor water quality. In this report an attempt is made to define as good water quality for fish culture. Information is also presented which will help in determining the potential of a body of water for producing fish, improving water quality, avoiding stress related fish disease and parasite problems, maintaining fish for research purposes, and ultimately producing more fish per unit of surface area.

As well, the most important rule in fish nutrition is to avoid overfeeding. Overfeeding is a waste of expensive feed. It also results in water pollution, low dissolved oxygen levels, increased biological oxygen demand, and increased bacterial loads. Usually, fish should be fed only the amount of feed that they can consume quickly (in less than five to 10 minutes). A good general rule of thumb is to feed the fish about 80 percent of the amount of feed they want to eat at satiation. Under this approach, on a regular basis perhaps twice a month, you feed for one day as much as the fish will consume. Thereafter, you feed approximately 80 percent of that ration for the next few weeks and repeat. Many growers use floating (extruded) feeds in order to observe feeding activity and to help judge if more or less feed should be fed.

Even with careful management, some feed ends up as waste. For example, out of 100 units of feed fed to fish, typically 40 to 50 percent is wasted: zero to five units of feed uneaten, and fish produce 10 to 15 units of solid waste and 30 to 35 units of liquid waste. Of the remaining feed, about 25 units are used for growth and another 25 units are used for metabolism. These numbers may vary greatly with species, sizes, activity, water temperature, and other environmental conditions.

CONCLUSION

The present paper explained the details about fish feed formulation, feed types, quality maintenance, feeding pattern and feed conversion.

The formulated fish is an important nutrient source for fish. Hence it is important to formulate the suitable feed and feeding management for proper growth and well-being of cultured fish.

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